

Reductive cleavage of Se-Se bond by Sm/NiCl₂ or Sm/NiCl₂.6H₂O system : A novel preparation of unsymmetrical aryl selenides

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The Sm/NiCl₂ or Sm/NiCl₂.6H₂O system promoted diarylselenides to react with alkyl halides to afford unsymmetrical aryl selenides in good yields under mild and neutral conditions.

Organoselenium compounds have received considerable attention as useful synthetic reagents and intermediates in organic synthesis¹. While there are many methods for the introduction of a seleno-substituent into organic molecules, the use of aryl selenide anions is especially convenient and common. Several methods for the synthesis of selenide anions have been recommended, the more important of which include the use of diphenyl diselenides with sodium borohydride², reduction of the diselenide with sodium³, samarium diiodide⁴ and lithium aluminium hydride⁵. Alternatively, sodium phenyl selenide may be obtained from the selenol using sodium hydride or even by treatment with aqueous sodium hydroxide under certain conditions⁶.

Samarium diiodide is a powerful one electron transfer reductant⁷. It has widely been applied in organic synthesis^{8,9}. Though SmI₂ is a useful reagent, storage is difficult because it is very sensitive to air oxidation. On the other hand, metallic samarium is stable in air and has strong reducing power (Sm³⁺/Sm = -2.41 V) similar to that of magnesium (Mg²⁺/Mg = -2.37 V). These properties promoted us to use the more convenient and cheaper metallic samarium directly as a reducing agent instead of SmI₂.

Results and discussion

Here we wish to report that the Sm/NiCl₂ system promotes the cleavage of Se-Se bond of diaryldiselenides to generate selenide anion, which reacted further with alkyl halides in THF under mild and neutral conditions to afford unsymmetrical alkylarylselenides (Scheme 1) in good yields. The results were summarized in Table 1. It is interesting that we also found that diaryldiselenides by Sm/NiCl₂.6H₂O system could react with alkyl halides to give unsymmetrical alkylarylselenides in good yields under the same conditions as above. The results (listed in Table 2) of our experiments indicated that such a small amount of

water in NiCl₂.6H₂O showed no notably bad influence on the reaction, but it could make the operation more convenient and simpler. Some control experiments revealed that Se-Se bond could not be cleaved by Sm or NiCl₂ alone. In conclusion, we have demonstrated Sm/NiCl₂ or Sm/

Table 1. Reaction with Sm/NiCl₂ system

Entry	Ar	RX	Product	Yield (%) ^a
1	Ph	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ Br	PhSeCH ₂ CH=CH ₂	78
2	Ph	PhCH ₂ Br	PhSeCH ₂ Ph	80
3	Ph	PhCOCH ₂ Br	PhSeCH ₂ COPh	76
4	Ph	BrCH ₂ CO ₂ Et	PhSeCH ₂ CO ₂ Et	74
5	Ph	BrCH ₂ CN	PhSeCH ₂ CN	68
6	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ Br	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄ SeCH ₂ CH=CH ₂	79
7	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	BrCH ₂ CO ₂ Et	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄ SeCH ₂ CO ₂ Et	69

^aIsolated yields.

NiCl₂.6H₂O system can be used for the preparation of unsymmetrical alkylarylselenides via the cleavage of the Se-Se bond. The experimental simplicity, mild reaction condition and good yield provides a new way for using metallic samarium in organic synthesis.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Metallic samarium and other chemicals were purchased from commercial sources and used without purification. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was distilled from sodium/benzophenone immediately prior to use. All reactions were carried on under a dry nitrogen atmosphere. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 683 spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were determined on a Bruker AC-400 instru-

ment. All NMR samples were measured in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal standard. MS spectra were recorded on a Finnigen MAT GC-MS mass spectrometer. High Resolution Mass Spectra (HRMS) were measured with JEOL JMS-DX303.

Table 2. Reaction with Sm/NiCl₂·6H₂O system

Entry	Ar	RX	Product	Yield (%) ^a
1	Ph	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ Br	PhSeCH ₂ CH=CH ₂	79
2	Ph	PhCH ₂ Br	PhSeCH ₂ Ph	78
3	Ph	PhCOCH ₂ Br	PhSeCH ₂ COPh	70
4	Ph	BrCH ₂ CO ₂ Me	PhSeCH ₂ CO ₂ Me	71
5	Ph	<i>n</i> -BuBr	<i>n</i> -BuSePh	55
6	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	BrCH ₂ CO ₂ Et	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄ SeCH ₂ CO ₂ Et	68
7	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	BrCH ₂ CN	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄ SeCH ₂ CN	73

^aIsolated yields.

General procedure : Metallic samarium powder (1.0 mmol), NiCl₂ or NiCl₂·6H₂O (1.0 mmol) and diaryl diselenide (0.5 mmol) were placed in a three-necked reaction flask and THF (10 ml) was added in one portion. Alkyl halide (1.2 mmol) was then added to the mixture and stirred at 50°C for 5 h indicated in Tables 1 and 2. A diluted solution of HCl was added to quench the reaction and the mixture was extracted with diethyl ether (20 ml × 2). The organic layer was washed with water (20 ml × 2) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The residue was then purified by preparative TLC on silica gel (cyclohexane-ethyl acetate as eluent) to give pure product.

PhSeCH₂CH=CH₂; oil (lit.¹⁰); IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3095, 2945, 1645, 1480, 985, 910, 730, 680; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 3.31 (2H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 4.79 (2H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 5.46–6.15 (1H, m), 7.06–7.56 (5H, m).

PhSeCH₂Ph; oil (lit.¹¹); IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3090, 2985, 1580, 1490, 1445, 1160, 940, 750, 690; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 3.95 (2H, s), 7.05–7.45 (10H, m).

PhSeCH₂COPh; oil (lit.⁴); IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3085, 2955, 1680, 1600, 1590, 1480, 1400, 1275, 1180, 925, 730, 700, 685; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 4.05 (2H, s), 7.00–7.95 (10H, m).

PhSeCH₂CO₂Et; oil (lit.¹²); IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3075, 2960, 1750, 1590, 1480, 1460, 1350, 1220, 1170, 935, 740, 685; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 1.12 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 3.29 (2H, s), 3.96 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz), 7.01–7.65 (5H, m).

PhSeCH₂CO₂Me; oil (lit.¹³); IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3100, 3030, 2960, 1750, 1490, 1450, 1260, 1010, 890, 745, 690; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 3.60 (3H, s), 3.66 (2H, s), 7.10–7.65 (5H, m).

n-BuSePh; oil (lit.¹⁴); IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3055, 2950, 1590, 1480, 1420, 1370, 1220, 1110, 925, 740; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 0.80

(3H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz), 1.00–1.85 (4H, m), 2.70 (2H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz), 6.95–7.55 (5H, m).

PhSeCH₂CN; oil (lit.¹³); IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3010, 2995, 2960, 2250, 1580, 1480, 1450, 1020, 880, 740, 680; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 3.40 (2H, s), 7.16–7.70 (5H, m).

p-MeC₆H₄SeCH₂CH=CH₂; oil (lit.^{10,15}); IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3080, 2960, 2870, 1640, 1510, 1380, 990, 830; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 2.10–2.33 (3H, s), 3.31 (2H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 4.77 (2H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 5.53–5.90 (1H, m), 6.73–7.50 (4H, m).

p-MeC₆H₄SeCH₂CO₂Et; oil; IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3030, 3000, 2945, 2870, 1740, 1600, 1450, 1260, 1020, 880, 800, 670; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 1.10 (3H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz), 2.30 (3H, s), 3.30 (2H, s), 4.02 (2H, q, *J* 6.4 Hz), 6.96 (2H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 7.38 (2H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz); MS (EI) *m/z* 258 (⁸⁰Se-M⁺, base), 256. HRMS (EI) Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₄O₂Se (M⁺) 258.0159. Found : 258.0165.

p-MeC₆H₄SeCH₂CN; oil; IR ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹ 3080, 3040, 3000, 2965, 2870, 2240, 1610, 1500, 1450, 1410, 1010, 890; ¹H NMR (δ_{H}) 2.16 (3H, s), 3.00 (2H, s), 6.91 (2H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz), 7.28 (2H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz); MS(EI) *m/z* 211 (⁸⁰Se-M⁺, base), 209. HRMS (EI) Calcd. for C₉H₉NSe (M⁺) 210.9900. Found : 210.9935.

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